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DESIGN AS A SYNTHESIS OF SPACES USING THE P-S FRAMEWORK

Eswaran Subrahmanian / Yoram Reich / Frido Smolders / Sebastiaan Meijer
Carnegie Mellon Univ. + CSTEP/ Tel Aviv University / Delft Univ. of Techn. /Delft Univ. of Techn.
sebastiaan.meijer@tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

Designing is a multi-dimensional phenomenon and is difficult to describe through one disciplinary research lens only. This paper uses a framework within which multiple theories of designing could be informed of their role and explanatory power. The Product space and Social Space framework describes the scope of designing activities and it allows for incorporating insights from cognition sciences. This framework is the basis for analysis of the three case studies presented in this paper. The analysis illustrates the power of the framework to integrate insights from role of cognitive structures to explain the failures or successes in the case study. These case studies are a beginning of an effort to prove the utility of the framework for pragmatic use in being able to draw insights from a multiplicity of theories of human activity to understand designing.

Keywords: Designing, research lenses, integrated theories.

INTRODUCTION

Designing is a fundamental human activity. Recent evidences from cultural studies of chimpanzee (McGrew, 2010) and other animals point to their tool design and use including in some cases variation across communities of the same animal. In humans, this ability called designing is most refined due to humans' facility with language and use of numerous kinds of representations in multiplicity of media to sustain their shared memory beyond themselves. This ability has been the cornerstone of human development especially in the last few hundred years. The question we ask here is: Can this act of designing be studied using a reductionist model of

science or does it have to aspire for a different model? We contend that designing is inherently synthetic and integrative across a magnitude of disciplines and hence cannot be inquired from within a single disciplinary research lens alone (Subrahmanian et al, 2011). The multi-dimensional character of designing is that it encompasses all aspects of existence from the trivial and mundane to the most complex. Therefore, any study of designing would require multiplicity of "lenses" to create composite pictures of designing that draw on insights from practices in different disciplines including arts and crafts and insights from scientific areas within social sciences and engineering sciences.

The challenge in understanding designing is to synthesize these insights with the goal of "consilience" even if the constituent theoretical insights and theories are incommensurate methodologically (Wilson, 1998). Both the result of the design activity and the theory about designing are artifacts and hence, do not suffer from the need for methodological consistency as required in the disciplinary natural and social sciences (Klabbers, 2003, 2006). For artifact design as in design research it is creating these synthetic theories that allows for analysis and provides the right insights to realize the artifact. This approach to design of artifacts is prevalent in the history of practice of design.

Historically, product and artifacts were not developed with all the theoretical underpinnings of the natural phenomena worked out, but continually refining the theoretical and practical knowledge (Subrahmanian et al., 1993). We will make the case that the activity of design provides the opportunity to create an alternative integrated and scholarly base that is not the norm in the practice of science

that is prevalent today (Gulati, 2007). The critical challenge for design research is to create composite workable accounts of designing that can be constructed from reductionist and other studies to get the essence of diversity and unity in designing - the instinctual act that is at the core of human survival.

In order that we are able to understand the importance of different theories in design, we need an open framework that characterizes the space of design activity. We have chosen the P (Product) space - S (Social) Space framework proposed in our earlier paper (Subrahmanian et al, 2011) to examine different cases and to show the need for aligning the two spaces as critical to the functioning of the organization in design activities. In aligning these models, several theories of cognition can contribute at the individual, in ensembles of work, and social levels, along with issues of institutional and other scientific perspectives. The PS framework is a model that is open to critique and changes to accommodate more dimensions to the design activity that are not currently present in the P-S framework.

To illustrate the usefulness of the P-S Framework we draw upon a few cases of designing that are well documented and stem from diverse areas of design such as, service design and engineering design. What is being illustrated is that changes in the Product space affect the Social space and vice versa. These changes in P and S result in the disruption of the cognitive structures that mediate design work.

The paper is organized with the next section describing the P-S framework and the subsequent section proving the three case studies. The conclusion section summarizes the utility of the framework in understanding designing and future work.

FRAMEWORK OF THE LENSES

In Subrahmanian et al (2011), the authors argued that the analysis of design should be seen through a multitude of lenses that together span a space containing the design process, the artifact designed as well as the environment of the artifact, which

could be the social environment for use or the technical environment like a production line.

For sake of readability, we will discuss the major points of this paper here, to the extent that we build upon it in the remainder of the paper. The P-S framework is derived from the assumption that a product can be characterized by a parameterized three-dimensional space called the product space (P-space) and equally another parameterized three-dimensional space that characterizes where the act of designing takes place, the social space (S-space). The dimensions of these spaces were determined from our understanding of the range of social contexts in which design takes place and the range of products and services that are designed. The P-space is where the functional needs and the characteristics of the product are determined and has three dimensions (Figure 1). They are a) the dimensions of the complexity of the product, b) the disciplines both formal and informal that need to participate in the specification and development of the product and c) the availability of knowledge to create the product. These three dimensions do not represent a completely defined space for a product but are sufficient to our purpose. Over time, a product positioned in this space could change its location along all three dimensions. For example, knowledge that was once at the cutting edge and scarce become common practice and product once innovative becomes obsolete. In addition, as time passes, products tend to involve many disciplines, and become more complex to reflect the changes in social needs and requirements that are imposed on the product.

Figure 1: The product space (P-space) characteristics

CASE 1: RAIL TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT: REDESIGN OF THE OPERATION AT UTRECHT CENTRAL

The Dutch rail infrastructure manager is trying to improve the complex design of the rail traffic control to increase the resilience and gain costly capacity. Utrecht Central station is the main hub in the Dutch rail network and therefore a crucial part, influencing the performance of the entire system. Several years before the operation redesign, the organization did a major redesign of the track scheduling to avoid crossing train paths at the station. The goal of the current design cycle is to find a way to match the control span of train dispatchers to better match the track scheduling. The hypothesis is that this will prevent disruptions from spreading through the rail system. The process of design is that dispatching experts designed a control span layout where from the 288 rail switches available on the emplacement only 9 had to be used for the dispatching. Before this layout could become a rail dispatching design, it had to be completed for both the rules and procedures in the multi-organizational context (train operators, maintenance companies) in the product space and the means of interaction and communication in the social space.

Earlier approaches to the problem assumed a problem structure as described within a single assumed point in the social space and used the known representational structures and semantics to solve the problem. An earlier such attempt at the Dutch Rail Operator did not yield the desired results leading to the approach described here.

The process to do this was using a gaming simulation in which 25 operator-level people participated, playing their real role in a simulated environment. The knowledge availability was good, but the number of disciplines high. The complexity of the artifact is partially formed by the number of roles and disciplines involved, plus the emergent and unpredictable behavior of the interlocking and dependencies of trains. In the Social Space, the problem holds middle ground between an open and a closed world as the train dispatching itself is fairly isolated, but the preferences and interactions with the functioning of the public transport system as a whole are there too. The number of languages is fairly limited, as all people in the train system

understand each other. What really makes the design complex is the number of perspectives as everybody in his own role has a different view on what is an optimal solution and who should have the final word. Together the operators explored several scenarios of train dispatching using the new control span. After each scenario the emergent rules and procedures were captured using debriefing, and the real-world managers shared what they found the success factors for the interaction and communication. After 3 scenarios, the comprehensive lists were combined and then discussed with the 25 operators. From this, leading rules and procedures could be compiled, including a top-ten list of assumptions that need to be shared between all operators to overcome the number of perspectives in practice. The outcomes included preliminary rules and procedures, a to-do list for the management to give new instructions to all disciplines involved, the top-ten list to base new rules on, and a home-work list for the dispatching engineers to work out particular details. The most important part herein is the discovery that predefined infrastructure plug scenarios should be defined for smaller pieces of the infrastructure, like individual switches in the Utrecht station area, instead of the corridor level.

The design approach proved a great success, as in the social space it led to fundamental discussions in the subsequent weeks, and finally a successful implementation of the new dispatching paradigm in the Utrecht operations.

In this case, the clear message is that after extensive mediation and scenario building, the underlying situated cognitive objects and structures were extracted and codified thereby creating a common semantics (language) through which the problem could be solved. Theories of cognition and linguistic evolution become critical in understanding these transformations.

CASE 2: AN ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT MANUFACTURER

The following case study was conducted in the early 1990's to understand the information flow and operation of design and manufacture of electrical equipment in Europe. The case study is based on a

company that changed its product space without changing the social space.

The company used to serve two or three customers in a small geographic region with very similar requirements specification for the equipment and stable set of customers. Therefore, the organization was kept small with a team that took care of the design and manufacture that was standardized at the time of founding the company. From a product space perspective, the product is relatively well understood - complexity is low, and the disciplines involved were few (mechanical, electrical, manufacturing and sales). The social space in terms of a relatively closed world, small number of languages (local market) and limited perspectives matched the requirements of the problem space.

At one point in the late 80's, the organization decided to increase the scope of its market from a small region to a global market. This increased complexity by increasing the variety of product specifications and by increasing the number and variety of customers and customized components. What had changed was that the product space was transformed to a state of increased complexity due to variety. Lower levels of knowledge availability of the customer needs and requirements that were much more varied, and the inclusion of marketing and the need for more global business knowledge needed increased with complexity and scope.

The social space was changed to create a linear model of Specification to Manufacture - what is called 'over the wall' engineering. This was a small change in the prior standardized model of social space. The result of this mismatch between the radical change in the product space and the minor variation in the social space was that the company deteriorated over 8 years of operation to the point where it was not able to fulfill orders on time. The variation in manufacturing process led to difficulty in managing scheduling of manufacturing and delivery. The company was not functioning as the prior standardized procedures were replaced by incremental procedures based on ad-hoc customer demands.

The remedy that was undertaken was to intervene in the social space to create a clear understanding of the product space. This was done by creating a team from corporate R&D with representatives from all functional sections of the firm. This team sought to create composable product variety based product specifications and standardized component designs. Further, a new process was created that would control the variation in product design in the future, whether these changes resulted from technology, changes in regulations and/or customer needs. The process now included a team of engineers, marketing staff, and customers to manage changes and variety. A new social setting was designed by acknowledging the openness of the problem space, need for additional perspectives and languages for dealing with the new position in the product space.

Now looking at what the design of new structures - both social and informational - entailed, we see that a social organization along with the structuring of information, representation and product for variety were aligned leading to creation of new cognitive structures - boundary objects at the interfaces of disciplines and processes - for common understanding and negotiated mediation between the disciplines.

This case study illustrates that co-design of product context and social context are critical to the effective functioning of engineering design and production. The design of these contexts also requires design of cognitive representations for the purposes of collective understanding of the product design and manufacture as well as individual work. Design here is clearly the synthesis of not just the product and social contexts but also the information representation and the design process. However, without understanding the two fundamental spaces of P and S and their relationships clearly, the incorporation of the information and process structures as cognitive mediators into a pre-existing product and social space combination will result in failures due to mismatch.

CASE 3: MANAGING ENGINEERING CHANGE IN TRANSIT SYSTEMS

This case is of a multinational firm that used to manufacture trains and other transit systems. Originally, the company was part of a large electrical, energy and transport conglomerate that was structured to primarily operate out of a geographical region in North America. This company was then broken up into different divisions and the transportation division was separated and sold to another transportation conglomerate. The North American firm had created a social context that ran across its divisions by consolidating particular component or technology function. For example, propulsion for all their systems was centered in one division to manage variety across divisions. This allowed for sharing knowledge across products and also to manage the issues of variety in production across energy, transportation and other products. When this conglomerate was unbundled for financial reasons, the train division was separated out, with the relevant knowledge pieces from different divisions for trains as part of it, with a new organizational structure before selling the division.

After it was sold, the firm was re-organized again with some level of retrenchment of engineers and others in the organization. Further, the processes were changed. Here the position in the product space remained the same but the position in the social space was radically altered with partial reliance on information technology and an information base. The problem was to create trains for specific customer for short distance mass transit and to make sure that variety created by requirements of individual customers is kept under control. A clear social model of managing variety operationally existed before the sale of the division. In the second situation, the entire knowledge base that interlinked manufacturing, product variety and engineering changed because the manufacturing information engineer's post was abolished, and he had been the interlocutor between the different groups. However, by changing the position in the social space with its reliance on the information technology, the position in the product space changed too. To elaborate further, with the removal of the manufacturing information engineer function,

the design engineer had to reconcile the variety problem across multiple instances of the product from the past as well as those in various stages of design and implementation. Even with the databases, this was cognitively impossible as the review by engineers from multiple disciplines was removed. This led to increased engineering change orders and sometimes to change orders on change orders (about 10-15% of them).

In this case, while the product context was clearly known, the changes in the social context changed the scope of the problem that can be addressed; a restricted one. This in turn, resulted in the need to change the processes and information objects serving as mediating representations in the social space so as to include other disciplines such as safety, manufacturing, inventory control and others. This case illustrates the interdependence of the two spaces P and S, and demonstrates that any change in the position in any of the spaces will trigger changes in the other space. This example shows that incremental changes without appropriate new cognitive structures being created, as part of the change, will lead to deterioration in their collective semantic interpretations and performance of the system until radical transformation becomes imperative. These radical transformations require rewiring the cognitive representations that mediate work in the social space itself: from the individual to the social situated in the context of work.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The contribution of this paper is the positioning and illustration of value of the P-S framework to large-scale real-world cases. The basic hypothesis, that in any successful (and non-futile) design there needs to be a balance between the Product and the Social space, should hold valid in the cases. In the original paper, we discussed a few cases to illustrate the usefulness of separating the dimensions into the two spaces. Taking three new cases and explaining them in the framework has allowed showing that the transformation from one point in the P-S spaces space to another is not a simple shift. The shift requires reconstituting the socio-cognitive wiring and representation of the institutions. These cases

bring out the essence of design activities that take place over time, people and context.

The first case illustrates the necessity to balance the P and the S space in the design of successful services in complex technical infrastructures. In the two engineering cases, the first case illustrated how a change in P space did not result in the required S space changes and an alignment of P and S was required to set the misalignment right. The second case illustrated that even without a change in the P-space, a change the S-space can lead to their misalignment and performance issues. This in turn will require a P-space re-evaluation and S-space realignment along with new process and new information objects as cognitive structures at the collective and individual level.

For each of the three cases, the P-S framework helps to understand the design in its holistic meaning. Throwing three completely different cases to it is a first proof that the framework is not limited to industries or specific design approaches. We invite other researchers to use the framework and to explore its explanatory power and limitations to integrate and contrast the contribution of different theories of design.

Future research is required to identify consequences for other theories about the act of designing. As we argued in the previous paper, design is a multi-faceted, multi-disciplinary activity. We will never find one theory that will explain it all, but linking theories, dimensions and approaches to a quilt will lead to a better understanding of design as an activity. The P - S framework is unique in its simple explanatory power for imbalances in the process of designing while not limiting the number or type of dimensions to be included. Each of the current dimensions needs to be explored for its relation with theories from the natural, engineering and social sciences. This may lead to the emergence of new design theories.

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